

Chemical Investigation of *Pyrus Malus*

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Pyrus malus (Fam. Rosaceae) is a medium-sized tree, growing abundantly in the north-western Himalayan region. Paper-chromatographic investigations¹⁻³ of the extracts of fruits of *Pyrus malus* and *Pyrus communis* indicated presence of chlorogenic and isochlorogenic acids in combination with their related substances; some glycosides of quercetin were also obtained. Reports⁴ are also available of the work with leaves of *Pyrus malus* and other *Pyrus* species where identification of flavone glycosides has been recorded. The first systematic investigation on the different parts of some *Pyrus* species had been taken up by Chakravarti *et al.*⁵⁻⁶ in this laboratory. The present work deals with the isolation of three different compounds from the bark of *Pyrus malus*. It has been possible to identify β -sitosterol, friedelin, and *epi*-friedelinol by extracting the bark with different solvents.

Procedure.—Air-dried, powdered bark was extracted successively with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform, and ethanol (90%). The petroleum extract on concentration to a small volume yielded a faintly yellow crystalline mass; the chloroform extract yielded a dark yellow solid; the cold ethanolic fraction provided a very small amount of a brown alkali-soluble residue.

The petroleum extract furnished two distinct crystalline fractions. Fraction (I), crystallised from benzene, m.p. 275-77°, responded to the Burchard-Lieberman reaction and developed no colour with tetranitromethane. It did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample⁶ of *epi*-friedelinol. (Found: C, 84.38; H, 12.42. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{52}O$: C, 84.11; H, 12.14%). The acetate, m.p. 286°. (Found: C, 81.58; H, 11.60. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{54}O_2$: C, 81.70; H, 11.48%). Fraction (II), crystallised from methanol, m.p. 138°, responded to the Burchard-Lieberman reaction; the acetyl derivative, m.p. 126°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample⁵ of the acetate of β -sitosterol remained unchanged.

The chloroform extract on chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina yielded two fractions. Fraction (I), crystallised from methanol, m.p. 137-38°, was found to be identical with fraction (II) from the petroleum extract. Fraction (II), crystallised from methanol, m.p. 252-54°, also responded to the Burchard-Lieberman test and exhibited no colour with tetranitromethane. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of friedelin^{3,6} remained undepressed. (Found C, 84.66; H, 11.82. Calc for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.50; H, 11.74%).

1. Geissman, "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds", p. 528.
2. Siegelman, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1955, **213**, 647.
3. Herrmann, quoted *Trav. Chim. alimentair Hyg.*, 1959, **50**, 121.
4. Williams, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1964, **29**, 1318.
5. This Journal, 1964, **41**, 83.
6. *Ibid.*, 1964, **41**, 859.

The oxime crystallised from benzene, m.p. 290°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of friedelin-oxime, 291°.

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